

Exuberant Urethral Malignancy causing unrelenting Bladder Outlet Obstruction, misdiagnosed as Malignant Prostatic Obstruction: Case Report

Celsus Undie¹, Kenechi Nedosa², Adeyemi Akano³, Precious Adeyemi⁴, Ema Umobong⁵, Collins Bamnan⁶

^{1,2,3,4} Kelina Hospital, Abuja, Nigeria. ^{5,6}Histoconsult Laboratory Limited, Abuja Nigeria.

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*Corresponding Author: Celsus Undie¹

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Abstract

Case Report

Prostate cancer extending to the penile urethra is not a common occurrence. While prostate cancer is a relatively common condition, its spread to the penile urethra can sometimes be overlooked or misinterpreted. We present a 72-year-old diabetic and hypertensive gentleman that we saw in our hospital, who was initially diagnosed elsewhere of enlarged prostate and had surgery done due to retention of urine, but re-presented in the same hospital for a repeat surgery, also for retention of urine. He was finally found to have prostate cancer following histological assessment of prostate tissue removed from him. He came to us due to concerns over persistent rise in PSA and episodes of acute retention of urine necessitating urethral catheterization. He presented to us on an indwelling Foley's catheter. Urethrocystoscopy was done to determine the cause of recurrent acute retention of urine, and urethral tumor was found, extending from the bladder neck into the distal urethra, causing bladder outlet obstruction. This case underscores the diagnostic challenge of bladder outlet obstruction in patients with enlarged prostate, and the importance of urethrocystoscopy in all patients who require surgery in the lower urinary tract, especially where there are no urethral strictures or stones. This helps to avoid misdiagnosis of the aetiology of bladder outlet obstruction, as not all cases are due to the enlarged prostate, even if enlarged prostate was found on digital rectal or radiological examination.

Keywords: Prostate Cancer, Bladder Outlet Obstruction, Urethrocystoscopy, Urethral Tumor, Prostate Tissue, Enlarged Prostate

Background:

Prostate cancer is usually diagnosed by prostate biopsy, often prompted by a blood test to measure prostate-specific antigen levels.¹ A digital rectal examination is generally done on these patients to assess size, consistency, nodularity or otherwise of the prostate gland². An accurate diagnosis is the first step for the successful management of prostate cancer which helps determine the aggressiveness and the most appropriate treatment options.³ Urethral tumors are not always obvious clinically nor is the urethra often sampled for routine histological sections due to location and size of tumors and nonspecific symptoms like dysuria, hematuria, and urinary frequency.⁴ Prostate cancer growth into the

urethra can vary from one patient to the other both on the basis of misdiagnosis, genetics, or spread to the urethra.

Adenocarcinoma of the prostate extending to the urethra is extremely rare: most cases are urothelial carcinomas and just very few cases of metastatic prostate cancer to the urethra have been reported.⁵ Generally, prostate cancer involving the anterior urethra is exceedingly rare. Isolated recurrence of metastatic prostate cancer to the anterior urethra has been reported in only ten cases.^{6,7}

However, the metastatic route and appropriate treatment remain unknown^{8,9}. There are no clear causes, but there may be a link between urethral

cancer and conditions that cause long-term inflammation in the urethra¹⁰. While prostate cancer is a relatively common condition, its spread to the urethra can sometimes be overlooked due to a low index of suspicion. When patients present with bladder outlet obstruction necessitating surgery, the tendency is for clinicians to assume that the obstruction is from the prostate. Urethrocystoscopy is not routinely done before patients are booked or subjected to prostate surgery, as in our index patient¹¹. During surgery, if Urethrocystoscopy is still not done before the resectoscope is introduced into the bladder, urethral pathology can be missed. The temptation to introduce the resectoscope blindly into the urinary bladder to commence prostate surgery (either Transurethral Resection of the Prostate, TURP or Holmium Laser Enucleation of the Prostate, HoLEP), is much higher in patients who are on indwelling urethral catheter, where it is easier to assume that there is no stricture in the urethra¹².

We present a 72-year-old man who was initially diagnosed of enlarged prostate and subsequently prostate cancer and had multiple prostate surgeries for bladder outlet obstruction. The uniqueness of this case lies in the fact that it was actually penile urethral tumor extending from prostate cancer and causing bladder outlet obstruction that was misdiagnosed as bladder outlet obstruction due to pure prostate cancer. The obstruction to urine flow necessitating prolonged urethral catheterization was from the urethral growth, not the prostate, as the bladder neck was found to be wide open during Urethrocystoscopy under our care. This case underscores the diagnostic challenge of bladder outlet obstruction in patients with enlarged prostate, and the importance of Urethrocystoscopy in all patients who require surgery in the lower urinary tract, especially where there are no urethral strictures or stones. This helps to avoid misdiagnosis of the etiology of bladder outlet obstruction, as not all cases are due to the enlarged prostate, even if enlarged prostate was found on digital rectal or radiological examination.

Clinical History

A 72-year-old male retired civil service official presented at our hospital with recurrent lower

urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) including hesitancy, straining to void, poor urine stream, intermittency, terminal dribbling, and feeling of incomplete emptying of the bladder, urinary frequency and nocturia. He also had occasional hematuria. The patient had no history of urethral discharge, straddle injury, weight loss or low back pain. He was diagnosed with an enlarged prostate elsewhere, in 2020, where he had Transurethral Resection of the Prostate (TURP). A repeat TURP was done for recurrent bladder outlet obstruction in 2023. Histology of the tissue removed confirmed a diagnosis of adenocarcinoma of the prostate, Gleason Score 9. He was placed on subcutaneous goserelin after this, but he developed acute retention of urine thereafter. Oral Bicaluthamide was added to his treatment regimen in 2021 due to rising Prostate Specific Antigen (PSA) levels. These measures did not solve the problem of recurrent acute retention of urine. At the 3rd TURP in 2023, he was found to have extensive tumor growths into the bladder neck. For this reason, bilateral double J stenting was done with long-term stents. He was referred to the Oncologists for external beam radiotherapy (EBRT). In spite of the radiotherapy, he still developed retention of urine and was still catheterized. After this, he decided to seek help in our center.

Ultrasound scan was done following clamping of the urine bag. It showed a distended urinary bladder with anechoic contents. Double J (DJ) stents were seen in both sides. There was focal irregular thickening of the bladder neck with polypoid lesions from the bladder wall and increased vascularity on Doppler interrogation demonstrated within the mass that was suggestive of a bladder tumor. Prostate size was 54g. Kidney function was normal. There was urinary tract infection (UTI) with E. coli, sensitive to various antibiotics. Patient was treated for UTI before surgery.

Patient was booked for Urethrocystoscopy and possible tumor resection to wean him off the urethral catheter. At cystoscopy, the bladder neck was found to be wide open. Exuberant exophytic growth was found in the entire urethra and bladder neck.

Fig 1: Intraoperative capture of the tumor found in the urethra

Low-power bipolar resection of the urethral tumor was done with 50 Watts of energy, to avoid excessive application of energy to the urethra. Transurethral resection of the prostate was also done. DJ stents were left in place as visualization of the ureteric orifices was poor and there was still extensive tumor involvement of the orifices. Stents would be changed at a later date. Consent was obtained for bilateral extra capsular orchidectomy as well and this was done, due to severity of the disease seen on the operating table in spite of aggressive treatment up to that time.

Outcome

Patient was discharged after 4 days of surgery on oral antibiotics, antihypertensive and oral hypoglycemic medications.

Post-operative Course

The bladder was drained with 24F 3-way Foley's catheter which was changed to 20F catheter when urine became clear. Catheter was to be left in place for 3 weeks and was finally removed. Patient has continued to pass urine normally after this procedure. He is being followed up by the Oncologists.

Specimens from the urethral growth and prostate were sent separately to the Pathologist for testing. Histology of the prostate tissue exhibited an invasive malignant epithelial proliferation infiltrating the prostatic fibromuscular stroma, primarily as cribriform and poorly formed glandular structures, with a secondary pattern of sheets of atypical cells having prominent nucleoli. Areas of extracellular mucin pools as well as perineural invasion were also seen. There was no significant inflammation.

Urethral tissue showed the same histological pattern of malignancy as seen in the prostate, within the mucosa and submucosa of the urethra. Some fragments showed haemorrhagic, necrotic and fibrinous tissue. The mucosa was lined by pseudostratified columnar to transitional epithelium lacking any atypical/dysplastic or malignant features.

Immunohistochemistry for prostate specific antigen (PSA) was carried out on both the urethral and prostatic tumours, both of which were positive for the immunomarker indicating a prostatic origin for both tumours. The lesional cells exhibited strong diffuse cytoplasmic granular staining pattern for PSA.

Photomicrograph and immunochemistry

Pathologist Observation

- A. Adenocarcinoma of the prostate (H&E x200). Malignant acini (blue arrows) forming cribriform structures, are seen invading the fibromuscular stroma of the prostate. A focus of perineural invasion in which a nerve bundle (black arrow) is being surrounded by malignant acini.
- B. Urethral mass (H&E x100). Malignant cells (blue arrows) forming cribriform structures as well as sheets are seen in the submucosa of the urethra. The overlying urothelium (black arrow) is unremarkable.
- C. Urethral mass (immunohistochemistry x200). The tumour cells are positive for prostate specific antigen (PSA) immunostaining. They show strong diffuse cytoplasmic granular staining (black arrows).

Discussion

Prostate cancer extending to the urethra is not so common¹³. The spread of the cancer can be linked to direct spread, lymphatic spread or implantation from transurethral surgery¹⁴. It is not uncommon for advanced prostate cancer patients to receive transurethral surgery to maintain urinary tract patency.¹⁵ A transurethral instrumentation can possibly lead to the implantation of tumor in the urethra⁶. Malignant implantation by instrumentation sometimes develops after the procedure¹⁶. According to Chi-fen-hung, as of 2010, 12 cases of metastatic prostate cancer to the anterior urethra had been previously reported.¹⁷ Of these cases, 11 had a history of previous instrumentation and prostate resection.¹⁶ although all the tumors of these cases were solitary and did not involve the corpus cavernosa.¹⁶

Prognosis of patients with metastatic prostatic cancer to the penis is very poor.¹⁶ A case was presented by

Ellis and Epstein in 2015. In the case series reported by Ellis and Epstein, 3 of the 29 cases were initially diagnosed as urothelial carcinomas.¹⁸ This experience was also shared by Tu and colleagues who misinterpreted one of their cases of penile metastatic tumor from the prostate as a primary urethral cancer¹⁹

Our case was a missed case of urethral cancer extending from the prostate with initial multiple prostate surgeries, which were perhaps unnecessary if the growths in the urethra were found and resected instead, as these were the reason for the obstruction to urine flow, as we later discovered under our care. It was not clear to us if this tumour was a primary urethral tumour or an extension of prostate cancer into the urethra, as there was tumour in the entire urethra extending into, and beyond the prostate into the urinary bladder. For this reason, tissue removed from both the prostate and the urethra was sent separately for histology and immunohistochemical testing, both of which confirmed that this was a case of adenocarcinoma of the prostate extending into the penile urethra.

Conclusion

Prostate cancer presenting as a pan-urethral tumor is a rare condition, and this case report is to remind the medical community on the need for meticulous evaluation of the urethra during prostate surgery, even on patients who are on catheter. This case report highlights the fact that in advanced cases of prostate cancer, the tumor can extend into the (entire) urethra, independently causing obstruction to urine flow. The ability of clinicians to recognize and appropriately address the spread of prostate cancer to the urethra is essential for optimal patient outcomes.

Ethics Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Written informed and verbal telephonic consent was obtained and documented with date and time from patient for publication and any accompanying images and they are available upon request. The patient provided informed consent, and the study was conducted according to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Consent for Publication

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for the publication of this case report.

Availability of Data and Materials

This case report does not involve any separate data collection beyond the existing patient medical records

Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests

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Author contributions

CU: Conceptualization, Critical revision and supervision

KN: Critical Revision

AA: Drafting of manuscript

PA: Drafting of manuscript

EU: Pathology Report

CB: Pathology Report

All authors read and approved the final manuscript

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